

natural enemies (see table). The Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, and the Systematics Section of

the Entomology Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, identified the specimens. □

Common predators of rice insect pests recorded 1980-82 in Assam, India.

Predators	Prey	Prevalence or intensity
I. Araneae (spiders)		
Tetragnathidae <i>Tetragnatha mandibulata</i>	Nymphs and adults of <i>Cofana spectra</i> , <i>C. yasumatsui</i> , <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> , <i>N. nigropictus</i> , and <i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	High
Oxyopidae <i>Oxyopes javanus</i> Thorell	-do-	High
Araneidae <i>Neoscona theisi</i> (Walckenaer)	-do-	Moderate
<i>Araneus</i> sp.	-do-	-do-
Lycosidae <i>Pardosa</i> sp.	-do-	Low
II. Odonata (dragonflies)		
Libellulidae <i>Orthetrum sabina</i> (Dowry)	Adults of <i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> , <i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> and <i>N. fluctuosalis</i>	High
<i>Crocothemis servilia</i> (Dowry)	-do-	-do-
<i>Pantala flavescens</i> (Fabricius)	-do-	Moderate
<i>Diplacodes nebulosa</i> (Fabricius)	-do-	-do-
III. Odonata (damselflies)		
Coenagrionidae <i>Ischnura delicata</i> Dis	Nymphs and adults of <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> , <i>N. nigropictus</i> , <i>Cofana spectra</i> , and <i>Sogatella furcifera</i> .	High
<i>Ischnura rofostigma</i> Selys	-do-	-do-
<i>Agriocnemis pygmaea</i> Rambur	-do-	Moderate
<i>Ceriagrion coromandelianum</i> (Fabricius)	-do-	Low
IV. Orthoptera (meadow grasshopper)		
Tettigoniidae <i>Conocephalus longipennis</i> (de Haan)	Nymphs and adults of <i>Nephotettix</i> sp. and <i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	Moderate
V. Hemiptera (predaceous bugs)		
Pentatomidae <i>cicrona caerulea</i> Linnaeus	Larvae of <i>Naranga diffusa</i> , <i>Mythimna separata</i> , <i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> , and <i>S. litura</i> .	Moderate
<i>Andrallus spinidens</i> Fabricius	-do-	Low
Pygomenida benghalensis (Westwood)	Adults of <i>Di cladispa armigera</i>	Moderate
<i>Menida histrio</i> F.)		
Reduviidae <i>Coranus</i> sp.	Larvae of <i>Naranga</i> sp. and <i>Spodoptera</i> sp.	Moderate
VI. Diptera (rubber fly)		
Asilidae <i>Promachus</i> sp.	Nymphs and adults of <i>Oxya fuscovittata</i>	Moderate
VII. Coleoptera (beetles)		
Cicindelidae <i>Cicindela sexpunctata</i> Fabricius	Nymphs and adults of <i>Leptocorisa acuta</i> and <i>L. oratoria</i>	Moderate
Carabidae <i>Casnoidae indica</i> Thumberg	Nymphs of planthoppers and leafhoppers	-do-
Coccinellidae <i>Micraspis discolor</i> Fabricius	Nymphs and adults of <i>Cofana</i> sp.	High
<i>Harmonia octomaculata</i> Fabricius	<i>Nephotettix</i> sp. and <i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	Low
-do-	-do-	Low
VIII. Hymenoptera (wasps)		
Sphecidae <i>Psenulus</i> sp. nr. <i>Aogatophagus</i> P.	Nymphs and adults of leafhoppers	Low

A simple technique for locating feeding sites of green leafhopper in rice plants

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The feeding behavior of the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) on susceptible and resistant rice varieties is not yet clearly understood. Although GLH is regarded as a phloem feeder on susceptible rice varieties and a xylem feeder on resistant varieties, the existing semiquantitative biochemical methodologies for locating GLH feeding sites are complicated. We tested a simple technique for monitoring GLH feeding using a dye that is selectively translocated in xylem vessels.

GLH-susceptible TN1 and resistant ASD7 were grown separately in clay pots in a greenhouse. When seedlings were 10 d old, they were carefully removed from the pots and roots were washed thoroughly to remove soil particles. Roots were then immersed in an aqueous solution of 0.2% Safranin O (Kansai Reagent Corp.,

1. Assembly for collecting GLH honeydew, IRRI 1983.

Hirakata, Japan) for about 6 h, until the dye colored all the xylem vessels red. Seedlings were removed and the excess dye was washed off. Two to three seedlings of each variety were placed in separate 250-ml glass beakers with enough water to immerse the roots. Each beaker was covered with a medially perforated 12-cm-diam plastic petri dish through which the seedling shoots emerged (Fig. 1). A 9-cm-diam Whatman filter paper disc was placed on the petri dish around the base of each seedling, which was enclosed in a cylindrical mylar cage 15 cm high and 9 cm in diam. Ten newly emerged GLH females were introduced into each cage and allowed to feed on seedlings for 24 h. A set of untreated seedlings was infested similarly as a control. The honeydew excreted by GLH females dropped on the filter paper discs and was absorbed. Red honeydew spots on filter paper discs indicated xylem feeding. When filter paper discs from control seedlings were treated with a 0.1% ninhydrin-acetone solution, bluish amino acid spots indicated phloem feeding.

2. Filter paper discs on which GLH honeydew was collected when the insect fed on resistant ASD7 and susceptible TN1 rice varieties. Bluish amino acid spots on ninhydrin-treated filter paper discs, (top) indicate more phloem feeding on TN1, while the encircled red spots on filter paper discs (bottom) indicate more xylem feeding on safranin-treated ASD7 plants, IRRI 1983.

On susceptible TN1, GLH was primarily a phloem feeder, although occasionally it also sucked small quantities of xylem sap (Fig. 2). On resistant ASD7, red honeydew spots indicated the insect switched to xylem feeding. However, the insect also did some phloem feeding, because

there were traces of amino acids in the honeydew.

We are evaluating the efficacy of this technique for determining the feeding habits of other rice leafhoppers and plant-hoppers. □

Occurrence of grain mite *Tarsonemus* sp. in stored rice

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A tarsonemid mite, *Tarsonemus* sp. (Tarsonemidae), was found in stored rice grains (see table). After one month of storage in gunny bags, 1,000 randomly collected grain samples of each cultivar were planted 10/plate in moist 6-cm-diam petri plates after tearing the lemma and palea of each grain. They were incubated at room temperature (26±3°C) for 8 d. Then adult and juvenile populations of mites were counted, using a stage microscope.

Mite populations ranged from 0 to 19.56/grain and varied by cultivar. Ratna had the most mites and Kalinga I and CR1009 were not infested. White tip nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi* and fungi such as *Alternaria padwickii* and

Population and survival of *Tarsonemus* sp. in stored rice, Cuttack, India

Rice cultivar	No. of mites/grain ^a (adults + juveniles)	Germination ^b (%)		Survival ^c (days)		
		Unsterilized grains	Sterilized grains	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃
Ratna	19.6	86.2	87.0	360	315	360
Jaya	16.3	85.7	82.7	360	315	315
Shakti	12.0	81.0	85.2	270	225	225
CR146-225	9.0	83.2	81.2	225	225	180
CR113-84-2	6.7	84.7	87.2	225	180	180
CR126-27-25	6.1	86.0	86.7	225	180	180
CRM13-3241	4.0	88.7	87.0	225	180	225
JBS508-13-14	3.7	84.7	83.7	225	180	225
CR1014	1.6	81.0	83.2	180	180	180
Kalinga I	0.0	86.5	88.7	—	—	—
CR1009	0.0	84.7	86.0	—	—	—

CD to compare germination percentage of sterilized and nonsterilized grains at 5% = 3.94, 1% = 5.12

^a Mean population in 1,000 grains. ^b Mean germination tested after 45 d of storage. ^c Samples stored under natural storage conditions in CRRRI godown. ^d S₁ = gunny bags, S₂ = ghumma, S₃ = doli.

Fusarium moniliforme were found in grains which contained the mite populations.

In another experiment, under natural storage conditions (27 ± 6°C and 86 ± 8%

RH) the tarsonemid mite lived for 180-360 d in gunny bags, 180-315 d in ghumma (burnt earthen storage containers), and 135-360 d in doli (woven bamboo structure plastered with cow